

Environment

March 2026

The Western Balkans Agenda on Innovation, Research, Education, Culture, Youth and Sport is a long-term strategy from the EU and the Western Balkans (WB) for cooperation with the region. It will contribute to the region’s economic and societal development, building on three main pillars: Political, Thematic, and Regional.

The project POLICY ANSWERS monitors the implementation of the Western Balkans Agenda, and the broader context, progress and achievements are summarised in regular reports. In this Monitoring Card, you find the results of the fourth round of data collection in 2025 and at the beginning of 2026, in comparison to the data collected in the previous third monitoring round.

In terms of Environment, the monitoring focuses on the “Regulatory Indicators for Sustainable Energy (RISE)” and various achievements outlined in the WB Agenda (see next page).

Achievements in a wider context of the Western Balkans Agenda

Regulatory Indicators for Sustainable Energy (RISE)

Sources

Authors’ calculation based on RISE (2025) <https://rise.esmap.org/> (accessed 8 November 2025).

* This designation is without prejudice to positions on status, and is in line with UNSCR 1244/1999 and the ICJ Opinion on the Kosovo declaration of independence.

Regional Indicators

Establishment of soil pollution database for the Western Balkans	Inclusion of the region in pan-European depollution-related networks	Western Balkans Green and Circular Economy Stakeholders Platform
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Western Balkans Economy Indicators

Indicator and overall assessment of the region	Western Balkans Green Agenda implemented			Counteracting climate change and environmental degradation				
	Transition to sustainable transport	Transition in the energy sector	Energy Community Just transition	Integrated National Energy and Climate Plans (NECPs)	Disaster Risk Management	EU Mission: 100 climate-neutral and smart cities		
Albania	Several active projects, no new projects initiated	New projects and initiatives in the field	Not coal dependent	NECP adopted Emission Trading System (ETS) not in place	Disaster Risk Management Centre (DRMC) not in place yet	Participating in the Mission		
Bosnia and Herzegovina	Increased number of public initiatives	New projects and initiatives in the field	Coal phase-out date not set	NECP not adopted ETS not in place	DRMC in place	Participating in the Mission		
Kosovo	Increased number of public initiatives	New projects and initiatives in the field	Coal phase-out date not set	NECP not adopted ETS not in place	DRMC in place	Not participating in the Mission		
Montenegro	Several active projects, no new projects initiated	New projects and initiatives in the field	Coal phase-out date set	NECP not adopted ETS in place	DRMC in place	Participating in the Mission		
North Macedonia	Several active projects, no new projects initiated	New projects and initiatives in the field	Coal phase-out date set	NECP adopted ETS not in place	DRMC in place	Not participating in the Mission		
Serbia	Increased number of public initiatives	New projects and initiatives in the field	Coal phase-out date set	NECP adopted ETS not in place	DRMC in place	Participation in the Mission's Twinning Learning Programme		

Legend: On track or maintaining achievement | Moderately improving Challenges remain | Stagnating Significant challenges | Decreasing Major challenges | Information not available

Highlights

Policy Brief and Report Green Agenda for the Western Balkans published by POLICY ANSWERS related to the Green Transition Dubrovnik Declaration endorsed by the Western Balkans Ministers of Environment on 14 October 2025: a shift from planning to measurable action under the Green Agenda for the Western Balkans

Urban PM2.5 Atlas Air Quality in Cities of Countries involved in the EU Enlargement policy launched at the Fifth EU Clean Air Forum in December 2025

Strengthening Research and Innovation in the Western Balkans: The POLICY ANSWERS project

POLICY ANSWERS is a strategic initiative funded by the European Commission through the Horizon Europe project "R&I POLICY making, implementation ANd Support in the WEStErN BalkanS". The project focuses on enhancing research and innovation (R&I) policymaking and governance systems in the Western Balkans, while also addressing aspects of education, culture, youth, and sports. By providing essential support to the region's development, POLICY ANSWERS plays a crucial role in strengthening the Western Balkans' potential for successful participation in regional and multilateral research and innovation activities.

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